

Indicators Of Values Of Integrity And Corruption Combat And Its Correlation With Patriotism Of The Universities In Saudi Arabia Teaching Staff Viewpoints

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Abstract

The current study aimed to investigate the prevalence of regulatory legislations adopted at the Universities of Saudi Arabia to enhance the values of integrity values and corruption combating, to find the practicing level of these indicators among the teaching staff, and to identify the relationship between the indicators and teaching staff patriotism. The study used a descriptive methodology, during the academic year 2019/2020 the researcher designed a questionnaire and implemented it on a sample of (360) teacher. The study found that the teaching staff familiarity with the values of integrity and corruption combat legislations was very high. This result indicates that Universities in Saudi Arabia adopt regulatory legislations and clear laws to enhance the values of integrity and corruption combat. The faculty teaching practices degree direction was intermediate to low; this result refers to the teaching staff weak practicing of the values of integrity and corruption combating. Patriotism level among the teaching staff was intermediate to very high; this result refers to the teaching staff patriotism in the Universities of Saudi Arabia, a significant positive correlation was also found at ($\alpha = 0.01$) between the regulatory legislations and patriotism. In light of the results, the researcher recommends responsible authorities to focus on the dimensions of morality, familiarize individuals with corruption combat behaviors, prepare intensified programs about the risk of corruption and the impact of its outbreak, and popularize the culture of transparency and integrity since it saves the nation and supports the will to stand against all forms of anti-patriotism corruption. Officials are recommended to create an administration associated with National Authority for Combating Corruption and activate its role to insure commit to integrity. The study recommends researchers to compare universities experiences in developing the values of integrity and corruption combat; to study the difficulties and obstacles that confront higher education in employing corruption combat mechanisms; and to study the effect of administrations corruption in society's comprehensive development effort.

Introduction

Communities, since development, encounter vast economic, social, and moral challenges that have some negative aspects stripped from integrity and justice that spreads the corruption phenomenon which threatens social security, economic development, and administrations performance and considers it a major hindrance of achieving comprehensive development.

Al-Masry (2010) confirmed that corruption is an old phenomenon inseparable from human communities. Corruption forms, expressions, and intense vary according to the variation in the political, social and economic development levels.

Al-Gargouli and Ala'a (2016) said that corruption is a persistent global phenomena, is does not belong to a particular community or a particular historical era; rather it proved to be more spreading and prevailing to the extent of endangering many communities and organizations of collapsing.

Indeed administrative corruption affects social development, it disturbs justice principles, collapses moral values, and loses communal stability, and it undermines values of honesty, trust, equality, and equal opportunities all of which are indicators of civilizations and communities extinction. Corruption threatens the human relations of trust, reassurance and reduces contributions in charitable work; it leads to weak public investment efficiency, weakens quality level, brings lack of professionalism and work value, declines interest in public right, and sense of injustice (Hawassa & Bousnobrah, 2018).

National and global requests arose to enhance integrity and transparency values and to restrict corruption spread, and demands arose to set up proper plans, programs, and strategies for that. The kingdom of Saudi Arabia recognized the hazards of corruption as other countries did, and considered it a scourge that to fight. Therefore, the kingdom ratified the international agreements to combat corruption; accordingly, the council of ministers issued the national strategy to protect integrity and combat corruption in 2007, the strategy included a clear method to fight corruption and reject corrupted individuals. That was followed by establishing an independent national anti-corruption commission in 2011; its principals emerged from religious, moral, and national responsibilities and rule of the law. The commission held responsibility to combat all types of corruption; it took remedial and preventive actions and measures to enhance integrity values, corruption combat, and wakened citizenship spirit for constructing and advancement.

El-Sherbiny (2019) confirmed that integrity is an integrated system of individual, communal, and administrative values reflected through many practices and moral behaviours in different work environments; the main motivation and driving force to adhere to it is conscience stemming from sound culture.

Zayed (2015) considered integrity values a set of principles and standards that represent a benchmark to protect humankind progress, dignity, and essence. Commitment to integrity creates a sophisticated moral level, confident in life, and the ability to develop life quality.

Al-Ghamdi (2017) said that integrity holds value, driving force, and behavioral dimensions correlated with individual, communal, national, and organizational life aspects achieved through behavioral integration and balance.

Dweik (2013) formulated a group of goals of integrity to: enhance the country reputation locally and internationally, activate integrity and transparency decisions of the country, and publish virtues in the community such as integrity and corruption combat. While Al-Hadidi (2020) identified integrity and combating corruption five pillars by, sharing (everyone's direct voice in decision-making or voice through representatives and mediating organizations), transparency (everyone's right to access information and get acquainted with decision-making mechanisms, it is a preliminary to set ethical standards and organizational work charter founded on trust, responsibility and honesty), accountability (holding officials accountable for their actions, examine their decisions, and give them opportunity to justify their actions), justice and equality (offering everyone opportunities to protect them and improve their situations, this requires existence of social justice, satisfy needs and guarantee security), and rule of the law (a fundamental rule, individuals and governments abide by law, which is the reference instead of interest and favoritism).

The Transparency International organization report on corruption perception index (2019) showed higher rates of corruption in many countries in the world including Arab countries; the report noted the importance of blocking gaps leading to corruption and to enhance systems integrity with the following:

1. Enhancement of electoral integrity, governments must guarantee free voting to activate the democracy role against corruption. Preventing vote-buying and misguiding information is necessary to rebuild trust.
2. Control of political finance to prevent financial excess, run campaigns in a right way, reveal campaigns financial sources, assets, and loans, empower independent control organizations and provide them with resources and capabilities.
3. Manage conflict of interests, to reduce unjustified effects in policy making through intensified control on financial interests and officials interests in the country.
4. Empower citizens by protecting political and civil freedoms including freedom of speech, authorities should engage civil society and protect citizens, activists and whistle-blowers.
5. Address preferential relationships by establishing mechanisms to ensure the just services and allocation of public resources away from personal relationships and favoritism toward special interests groups at the expense of public good.
6. Contextualize lobbyists' activities to promote free and meaningful access to decision-making and consultation with a wide range of groups. Consultations activities should be public and available for public participation.

Many studies examined the values of integrity and corruption combat. For instance, Qtaite (2016) identified corruption types, reasons, and defects in communal development in pre-university education. He explored modern methodologies to combat corruption and control corruption behavioral and organizational practices. The study implemented a descriptive approach and utilized a questionnaire to monitor and analyze the real status quo compared with the standards and indicators of administrative and educational thought. He proposes three preventative, corrective, structural alternatives to combat corruption. The researcher recommends scholars to conduct further studies in different disciplines of the community value system.

Alshaerb and his colleagues (2017) studied the university governance effect on partnership enhancement with nongovernmental institutions working in Gaza Strip; they used a descriptive approach, and implemented a questionnaire on 228-university employees. A significant statistical correlation was found between the government and strengthening the relationship with public society institutions. The study recommended universities to implement governance rules and to hold workshops and training programs to familiarize the administrative body of the university with the importance of governance and its practices.

Nguyen and his research team (2017) examined the degree of transparency and accountability correlation with corruption in the higher administrative levels, and examined the correlation between the quality of public health

and education in lower levels quality with corruption in Vietnam. The researchers used the quantitative research, and distributed a questionnaire on (14000) Vietnamese in the age of 18. He found that higher levels of transparency, sharing and accountability correlated with lower levels of corruption. Moreover, corruption has a negative correlation with the quality of the services provided. The study recommends using specialized statistics techniques to study the strategies of combating corruption, to reinforce transparency and accountability.

Duerrenberger and Warning (2018) studied the role of governance in combating corruption; they adopted a descriptive analytical approach, utilized reports and data issued by UNESCO and World Bank. They found that the increase in corruption rates led to decrease in school attendance in the developed countries. They recommend governments to interfere in the educational sector, to combat corruption and enhance the educational process.

Heywood (2018) affirmed that institutions should focus on positive promotion of integrity; supported by better understanding of the individual behavioral motives. The study presented few practical measures that confirm the need to focus reformation efforts on the nation and local levels. He mentioned the lack of interest among researchers, academics, policy makers, and national financial organizations over the past 25 years. He presented a set of strategies to combat corruption such as transparency, justice and sharing. He said that it is necessary to cut off the ways of corruption through gradual reformation, proper leadership, public demands, and shift from privacy to universality and neutrality.

Datsii, Hubert and Kharchenko (2020) defined main determinants of corruption prevalence over the period of the systemic reforms, they proposed strategies to improve the policy of corruption combat as a necessary condition to improve life quality in the Ukrainian civil society. They used a descriptive approach in surveying opinions of political experts and local individuals. They presented methods of corruption combat by incorporating new behavior rules and morale codes within the law. Officials and citizens alike should adopt these codes. They recommend officials to use current strategies of combating corruption, such as public opinion polls, public disclosure of facts, allocate funds for reforms and activities and expand legal and technical assistance.

Owusu, Chan, Yang and Pärn (2020) identified corruption spread causes and the effectiveness of combating measures. A survey questionnaire answered by 38 experts measured the effectiveness of corruption combat actions. The researchers found that transparency and investigation are the most effective measures in combating corruption. They recommend broadening the scope of knowledge about studies examining integrity and corruption combat.

Study Problem and Questions

Communities recognized the dangers of corruption and the destruction it causes as it deepened lately. Communities took measures to combat corruption, they held many conferences and meetings, established organizations and commissions, and increased interest in finding corruption causes, forms, results and correction methods.

While observing the Arab countries status shows that most of corruption crimes emerge from lack of patriotism, which manifests itself in lack of work proficiency, lack of maintaining public money, sacrifice of nations gains, and disruptive behavior. The problem increased recently as a reason of political and economic changes that encountered Arab countries and reflected on the behaviors of the individuals and their relationship with their countries, their dissatisfaction about life in general. Abu El-Maati and Ahmed (2018)

Al-Sanoussi (2019) stated that corruption is an assault on human rights; it entails behaviours of public and private money confiscation, underestimation of people's privacy and rights, hinders people's obtaining their benefits and gains, added to prevalence of favoritism and bribery.

Okasha (2016) confirmed that absence of hope and goal, disappointment in achieving expectations and marginalizing citizen's needs and claims has a clear effect on mental health, which influence enthusiasm to work, produce, and citizenship.

Forms and appearances of corruption differ according to the culture, habits, and legal systems, Al-Gargouli and Ala'a (2016) classified these forms in:

1. Organizational irregularities are employee's violations in performing tasks such as: work disrespect by being late or unnecessarily early leavings, unproductivity in work time, refusal to complete tasks, late or wrong performance of the task, laziness, desire for extra profit by exhausting less effort, non-compliance to manager orders, and find excuses in order not to follow orders. Passivity, carelessness, reject expressing own opinion, refusing renovation, development and innovation, reluctance to engage in decision making, lack of cooperation and rejection of team work refer to organizational irregularities as well. Failure to take responsibility and hold others responsible, avoid signature being afraid of responsibility, disclose work secrets are organizational irregularities also.

2. Behavioral irregularities are employees' behavioral and characteristic violations such as: public position abuse to receive special benefits; power abuse to offer personal services, grease wheels, bypass objective equity considerations; favoritism in hiring public posts by unqualified employees which reduces management efficiency in providing services and increasing productivity; mediation as a form of mutual interest.

3. Financial irregularities are the employee financial violations correlated with the tasks assigned; they include absence of integrity and transparency in public tenders using illegal means and frauds in bidding for government procurements. Financial irregularities include as well violations of financial stated rules; public finance over-spending on buildings and furniture, exaggeration in setting up parties and events, and splurging on media and advertisement.

4. Criminal irregularities such as public finance assault, smuggling, bribery, and forgery.

Al-Masry (2010) said that the relationship of man and his homeland depends on love, sacrifice and a sense of pride, it reflects in giving, sharing, abiding to rules and prevailing values, preserving homeland interests and wealth. Belonging reinforcing factors include identity clarity, equality, law and order, and equal opportunities. Notably, all administrative systems confirmed homeland belonging and considered it of the employee duties. Definitely, these systems are precise because belonging is the core of work; because the main goal of educational, health-care, economic, or social sectors is offering services and completing tasks to develop the country and support national economy.

In this context, corruption combat has a major role in achieving patriotism, when corruption exists it becomes hard to speak about justice equality or equal opportunities, national stability sways, and values of honesty and equality degrades.

Accordingly, it can be said that corruption promotes behaviours that does not consist with patriotism, which often grow in corrupted environments reflecting ant-patriotism behaviours.

Consequently, the study problem is represented by the following main question “What are the indicators of values of integrity and combating corruption and its relationship with patriotism from the Universities of Saudi Arabia faculty teaching staff viewpoint?” the sub questions are as follows:

1. What are the regulatory legislations available and adopted by Universities of Saudi Arabia to enhance the values of integrity and combating corruption from the faculty teaching member’s viewpoints?
2. What is the extent to which faculty teaching staff in the Universities of Saudi Arabia practice values of integrity and combating corruption?
3. Is there a statistical correlation between the values of integrity and corruption combat indicators on one side and patriotism on the other from the viewpoint of the faculty teaching staff in the Universities of Saudi Arabia?
4. Are there significant differences between the faculty teaching staff responses in the Universities of Saudi Arabia on legislations, practices and patriotism according to academic degree obtained and affiliation?

Study Goals

1. Reveal the extent of the regulatory legislations available and adopted by Universities of Saudi Arabia to enhance the values of integrity and combating corruption from the faculty teaching staff viewpoints.
2. Reveal the level of values of integrity and combating corruption practiced by the faculty teaching staff in the Universities of Saudi Arabia.
3. Identify the correlation between the values of integrity and corruption combat indicators and patriotism from the faculty teaching staff viewpoints in the Universities of Saudi Arabia.
4. Identify the significant differences between the responses of the faculty teaching staff in the Universities of Saudi Arabia in legislations, practices and patriotism according to academic degree obtained and affiliation.

Study Importance

Theoretically, the study importance stems from the importance of values of integrity and seriousness of corruption crimes on the security of the communities, social structure, and economic growth. Islam forbids corruption; Islamic world agreed to criminalize corrupted persons. The study provides a set of indicators through which the universities ability to enhance values of integrity and combat corruption is measured. The study is a response to recommendations of international conferences requests to enhance values of integrity and corruption combat.

Practically the study benefits are apparent in the results revealed and recommendations provided. It gives an insight about the participants perceptions related to the topic of the study. It provides corruption combat committees with indicators to measure values of integrity and corruption combat and to evaluate the indicators practical aspects in different sectors. Leaders may benefit from the study in developing regulatory legislations and practical implications to reinforce individual’s tendencies toward their communities and institutions. Scholars studying different values may benefit from the recommendations and suggestions that may broaden further research on values of integrity and corruption combat.

Study Limitations

Three potential limitations inhibit generalizing the results of the study. The first concerns the objectives of the study limited to identifying the indicators of values of integrity and corruption combat and its relationship with patriotism. The second limitation concerns implementing the questionnaires on a sample selected randomly from faculty teaching staff (No. = 360) from five Universities in Saudi Arabia (King Saud University, Umm Al-Qura University, Majmaah University, King Khalid University, Shaqra University). The third limitation concerns time of implementing the study in the first semester of the Academic year 2020/ 2021.

Study Terminology

Indicators was defined by Abu Mahadi (2017) as the standards set by professionals to judge a certain activity success, then to compare the results obtained with the standard results over a period. Procedurally it is defined as a set of relied upon conditions, and controls that attempt to evaluate universities adopted legislations and practices to enhance values of integrity and corruption combat.

Integrity was defined by Al-Farhan (2015) as avoiding direct and indirect work abuses and offending practices that undermine performing tasks and duties, and working seriously and sincerely, hold responsibility and be faithful. Procedurally it is defined as the individuals' ability to adopt values, principals, and morals, and to abide to rules and regulations that organize educational and academic practices practically in a manner that reflects patriotism spirit.

Corruption was defined Masghouni, Barakah, and Makhlafi (2019) as the overall financial and behavioral irregularities, violations of the rules and regulations that govern administrative and financial functioning in the country and its institutions, violations of the financial control systems instructions responsible for government, bodies and public institutions accounts review and control. Procedurally it is defined as behavior violations of administrative rules and regulations that contradict with morals and work values for material and moral gains.

Patriotism was defined by Al-Sabeelah, Alraggad, and Abou-Ameerh (2015) as the individuals' feeling of positive attitudes for the country; it is strengthened with love, sacrifice, respect of rights, and proud feelings of own identity. Procedurally it is defined as the behavior of expressing the individual's love of the country, compliance to the prevailing values, commitment to rules and regulations, maintaining wealth and properties, and readiness to sacrifice for the sake of the country.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a descriptive approach that aims to identify the perceptions of the faculty teaching staff in the Universities of Saudi Arabia about values of integrity and corruption combat legislations, practices and patriotism. The study collected the data by a questionnaire designed to deal with the study problem.

Population and Sampling

The general population of the study comprised (36892) teaching staff affiliated to Majmaah University, King Abdulaziz University, Umm Al-Qura University, King Khalid University, Shaqra University in Saudi Arabia in the year 2020/ 2021. The sampling strategy for recruiting participants was random, the sample comprised (360) faculty teaching staff, a pilot sample was randomly recruited, it comprised (40) faculty teaching staff. The instrument of the study was reviewed by (20) reviewers.

Table (1) illustrate the Participants (No. = 360) distribution according to the Academic degree obtained and affiliation, teaching staff degree ranked first scored a percentage of (32.8%), assistant professor ranked second and scored a percentage of (30%), associate professor ranked third and scored a percentage of (21.9%), and the last rank was for the professors and it scored a percentage of (15.3%).

The sample distribution based on affiliation as noted in Table (1). Umm Al Qura University ranked first and scored a percentage of (22.8%), King Abdulaziz University ranked second and scored a percent of (21.7%), King Khalid University ranked third and scored a percentage of (21.4%), Shaqra University ranked fourth and scored a percentage of (18.3%), and Majmaah University ranked last and scored a percentage of (15.8).

Table (1) Sample distribution

	Variables	No.	%
Academic Degree	Lecturer	118	32.8%
	Assistant professor	108	30%
	Associate professor	79	21.9%
	Professor	55	15.3%
	Overall	360	100%
Affiliation	Majmaah University	57	15.8%
	Umm Al Qura University	82	22.8%
	King Khalid University	77	21.4%
	Shaqra University	66	18.3%
	King Abdulaziz University	78	21.7%
	Overall	360	100%

Instrument

The study nature, goals, and sample determine the instrument to be used. The current study aimed to screen availability of regulatory legislations adopted by university administrations to enhance values of integrity and corruption combat indicators, to find the extent to which the faculty teaching staff practices of values of integrity and corruption combat. The questionnaire screens the participant's views about the relationship between the indicators and patriotism. Accordingly, the study established a questionnaire comprising three

domains; first, legislations which refers to the set of issued rules from a competent authority, it includes (23) items. Second, practices which refers to the method of doing something, it includes (25) items. Third, patriotism which means positive attitude supported by love of the country, feeling proud being a citizen in it, care for its problems, abiding to rules and prevailing values that develops the country, it comprise (24) item.

Validity and Reliability

Instrument Validity

The primary questionnaire was reviewed by (20) competent experts; they reviewed the items and agreed on its appropriateness to measure values of integrity and corruption combat in the universities in Saudi Arabia, the results are illustrated in Tables 2, 3, and 4.

As observed in Table 2 the competent expert's agreement on items appropriateness to identify the legislations implemented in the universities to enhance the values of integrity and combat corruption, the (23) items agreement scored (85-100%).

Table 2. Experts (No. 20) agreement rate on integrity and corruption combat legislation

#	Item	Agreement	%
1	Consider all forms of corruption a crime punishable by law	20	100%
2	There is a strategic declared plan to combat corruption	20	100%
3	Regulations organizing the work agree with national regulations and laws combat corruption	20	100%
4	There are mechanisms to define academic, administrative and legal powers and duties	18	90%
5	The role of the regulatory bodies and their jurisdictions are identified	19	95%
6	There is a mechanism for systematic review for values of integrity and corruption combat measures	20	100%
7	Controlled measures for incentives and rewards	18	90%
8	Creating legislations to regulate financing and spending	20	100%
9	Create a control and accountability system according to rules and regulations	20	100%
10	Insure the free circulation of corruption cases information	18	90%
11	Established mechanisms to maintain and protect the intellectual property rights	20	100%
12	There are clear mechanisms to compensate corruption cases victims	20	100%
13	There is a policy for media freedom and protection	20	100%
14	Universities adopt efficacy and excellence criteria in selecting high administrative leaders	20	100%
15	There are private independent neutral commissions responsible for hiring and promotions	18	90%
16	Universities apply job rotation policies for various positions	18	90%
17	Individuals have the right to access information without contradiction with personal data confidentiality and preserving privacy	17	85%
18	Universities supervise all educational, research, administrative and financial requirements in an organized manner	20	100%
19	There is a clear system to hold partnerships with relevant centres and organization	18	90%
20	There are legislative mechanisms for fundamental reformations in administrative and financial decisions	20	100%
21	There is an academic freedom in the follow up and development of knowledge	20	100%
22	Clear policies adopted in studies and scientific research centres	20	100%
23	There are administrative frameworks to guarantee justice, equality and equal opportunities	18	90%

Table 3. Experts (No. 20) agreement rate on values of integrity and corruption combat practices

#	Item	Agreed	%
1	Universities Issue periodical objective statistics reports to guarantee integrity	18	90%
2	Universities announce appointments and vacancies to ensure integrity and transparency	20	100%
3	Relying on competence and academic qualifications and avoiding favouritism	20	100%

	and favouritism		
4	Favouritism in distributing tasks, powers, and in selecting presidents, members of councils and committees	18	90%
5	Activating an approved code of professional conduct	20	100%
6	Oblige staff to submit financial disclosure statements	20	100%
7	Subject all works and budgets to supervisory authority and hold it accountable before legislative councils	20	100%
8	Periodic checking on random samples of general expenses	17	85%
9	The effectiveness of the complaints and suggestions system in the available sites	20	100%
10	There are legislations to protect whistle-blowers and counter-allegations	20	100%
11	There are deterrent penalties for the convicted in corruption cases	20	100%
12	Create committees to study issues to rationalize spending and reduce the waste of public money	18	90%
13	There are restrictions on investigators publishing of corruption-related news and investigations	18	90%
14	Controlling Internet, social networking sites and mobile phones	18	90%
15	Retrieving rights and returning money to their owners and sources	20	100%
16	Preserving public and private property and assets, the fixed and movable	20	100%
17	The presence of influential party teams to take some decisions	18	90%
18	Some academic leaders exploit mandates and powers granted to them	20	100%
19	The university employees performance is evaluated objectively	20	100%
20	Honesty and objectivity in choosing the projects and initiatives supported	20	100%
21	Scientific honesty in documenting data and information	20	100%
22	Activating structured methods in the measurement and evaluation processes	20	100%
23	Misplacing some items of the allocated budgets	20	100%
24	Withholds some information and statistics from researchers and who wish to benefit from it	18	90%
25	Engage with outside institutions and centres business without the approval of the responsible authorities	18	90%

Table 4 showed the experts agreement on the second domain “practices” which is comprised of (25) items, the agreement scores range (85-100%).

Table 4. Experts (No. 20) agreement rate on patriotism

#	Item	Agreement	%
1	I adjust my behaviour to be a good citizen	18	90%
2	I respect rules and regulations established by the work system	20	100%
3	I commit to work deadlines and complete my tasks on time	20	100%
4	I advance the public interest over my own interest	20	100%
5	I perform my duties in an optimal manner	19	95%
6	I am emotionally attached to the place I work in	18	90%
7	I participate in decision making process as the system establish	20	100%
8	I renounce conflict and disunity between my coworkers	20	100%
9	I encourage scientific and intellectual achievement of my countrymen	18	90%
10	I participate in national and intellectual conferences	20	100%
11	I contribute in reforming the job environment in a systematic method	20	100%
12	I update my knowledge of the latest developments in professional and academic fields	20	100%
13	I ensure applying creative ideas that participate in developing my work	20	100%
14	I encourage developmental projects to participate in the country development	20	100%
15	I maintain private and public property in the work environment	20	100%
16	I am proud of all the country landmarks and what reflects its identity and history	20	100%
17	I participate in solving the problems and obstacles that prevent achieving my work goals	20	100%
18	I engage in actions that contribute to the renaissance of the country	20	100%
19	I encourage the country products	20	100%
20	I participate in voluntary and communal work	20	100%
21	I adhere to work group opinion even if it disagrees with what I believe	19	95%
22	I exhaust my efforts for a successful work	20	100%
23	I adhere to the moral values and virtues that represent the country values	20	100%

24	I stress representing my country in different occasions and events honourably	20	100%
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In table 4 the experts agreed on the third domain “patriotism” which included (24) items, the agreement rate range was (90-100%).

As tables 2-4 showed, experts agreed on the overall items of “indicators of the values of integrity and corruption combat in the universities of Saudi Arabia” questionnaire that in its final version included (72) items allocated on (3) domains and scored an agreement rate of (85%).

Internal Consistency

The questionnaire was completed by a pilot sample of (40) professors teaching in universities in Saudi Arabia. The correlation between each item and overall degree of the domain is calculated, and the correlation between each item score and the overall score of the whole questionnaire is calculated as showed in tables (5), and (6).

Table 5. Indicators of integrity and anti-corruption values for 40 participants from Universities of Saudi Arabia correlation coefficient

Dimension	Item	R	Dimension	Item	r	Dimension	Item	r
Legislations	1	0.411*	Practices	1	**0.563	Patriotism	1	0.326*
	2	0.405*		2	**0.458		2	0.398*
	3	**0.509		3	**0.563		3	0.407*
	4	**0.593		4	0.333*		4	**0.419
	5	**0.523		5	**0.623		5	0.395*
	6	**0.536		6	0.321*		6	**0.426
	7	0.329*		7	**0.452		7	**0.518
	8	**0.575		8	**0.430		8	0.373*
	9	*0.421		9	**0.519		9	0.368*
	10	**0.572		10	**0.511		10	**0.446
	11	**0.472		11	0.400*		11	**0.439
	12	*0.331		12	**0.765		12	**0.437
	13	*0.400		13	**0.481		13	**0.562
	14	0.408*		14	0.400*		14	**0.662
	15	**0.554		15	0.361*		15	**0.530
	16	**0.506		16	0.337*		16	**0.461
	17	0.343*		17	0.400*		17	**0.683
	18	0.404*		18	0.364*		18	**0.474
	19	**0.524		19	**0.413		19	**0.478
	20	**0.433		20	0.329*		20	**0.472
	21	**0.516		21	0.375*		21	0.390*
	22	0.412*		22	0.399*		22	0.392*
	23	0.413**		23	**0.537		23	0.362*
					24		**0.525	24
			25	0.395*				

* functional at (0.01) ** funcional at (0.05)

Table (5) presented a statistical significant relationship between each item and its domain, the correlation coefficient score range between (0.321-0.765). Table (6) presents the correlation coefficient score between the domain and overall score of the indicator.

As seen in table (6) there are statistical significant correlations between each domain and the overall degree of the tool. This result refers to the consistency of the items and domains.

Table 6. correlation coefficient scores for 40 participants responses between the dimensions

#	Dimension	Correlation coefficient	Sign.
1	Legislations	0.693**	0.01
2	Practices	0.662**	0.01
3	Patriotism	0.678**	0.01
Functional at (0.01)**			

Test Reliability

The obtained responses of the pilot sample (No. = 40 participant) is used for the calculation of reliability using Cronbach's Alpha and split half through two methods Spearman-Brown and Getmann as table 7 illustrate.

Table 7. Values of integrity and corruption combat reliability coefficients (No. 40)

#	Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha	Split-half
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			Spearman Brown's	Getmann
1	Legislations	0.649	0.607	0.602
2	Practices	0.664	0.652	0.651
3	Patriotism	0.672	0.631	0.631
Overall Cronbach's Alpha score (0.702) *				

Table 7 demonstrated that the correlation coefficients scores are all acceptable. Cronbach's Alpha score range (0.649-0.672), the index vector correlation coefficients in the two methodologies (Spearman-Brown and Getmann) are close, Spearman Brown's values range is (0.607-0.652), and Getmann values range is (0.602-0.651), all the values are acceptable. A comparison between Cronbach's Alpha values and the indicators' overall value shows that Cronbach's Alpha value is less than the overall value; this result indicates a high reliability degree of the tool.

Data Analysis

The study used repetitions, percentages, Cronbach's Alpha, split-half (Spearman and Getmann), simple Pearson correlation, chi square, and One Way Anova formula's in analyzing the collected data.

Results and Discussion

To answer the main question of "What are the regulatory legislations available and adopted by Universities of Saudi Arabia to enhance the values of integrity and combating corruption from the faculty teaching member's viewpoints?" repetitions and percent of the participant's responses as illustrated in table eight.

Table 8. Repetitions, percent, and responses (No. 360) ranks on legislations

Item No.	Very high		High		Moderate		week		Very week		Points	%	Rank	χ^2
	Chi-square	%	Chi-square	%	Chi-square	%	Chi-square	%	Chi-square	%				
1	288	80%	40	11.1%	10	2.8%	20	5.6%	2	0.6%	1672	92.9%	3	**821.22
2	52	14.4%	251	69.7%	45	12.5%	7	1.9%	5	1.4%	1418	78.8%	19	**581.72
3	258	71.7%	52	14.4%	25	6.9%	20	5.6%	5	1.4%	1618	89.9%	9	**616.64
4	224	62.2%	89	24.7%	26	7.2%	21	5.8%	0	0%	1596	88.7%	12	**297.93
5	243	67.5%	54	15%	33	9.2%	20	5.6%	10	2.8%	1580	87.8%	14	**522.69
6	266	73.9%	72	20%	22	6.1%	0	0%	0	0%	1684	93.6%	2	**276.87
7	230	63.9%	85	23.6%	33	9.2%	11	3.1%	1	0.3%	1612	89.6%	11	**491.89
8	254	70.6%	47	13.1%	48	13.3%	7	1.9%	4	1.1%	1620	90%	8	**599.64
9	45	12.5%	272	75.6%	24	6.7%	11	3.1%	8	2.2%	1415	78.6%	20	**706.25
10	60	16.7%	259	71.9%	35	9.7%	6	1.7%	0	0%	1453	80.7%	18	**439.36
11	247	68.6%	63	17.5%	30	8.3%	20	5.6%	0	0%	1617	89.8%	10	**376.42
12	62	17.2%	251	69.7%	47	13.1%	0	0%	0	0%	1455	80.8%	17	**215.45
13	20	5.6%	227	63.1%	86	23.9%	17	4.7%	10	2.8%	1310	72.8%	23	**469.36
14	83	23.1%	268	74.4%	0	0%	9	2.5%	0	0%	1505	83.6%	16	**296.62
15	40	11.1%	252	70%	52	14.4%	16	4.4%	0	0%	1396	77.6%	22	**396.27
16	36	10%	269	74.7%	42	11.7%	13	3.6%	0	0%	1408	78.2%	21	**479.89
17	103	28.6%	234	65%	23	6.4%	0	0%	0	0%	1520	84.4%	15	**189.12
18	263	73.1%	84	23.3%	13	3.6%	0	0%	0	0%	1690	93.9%	1	**276.62
19	246	68.3%	55	15.3%	32	8.9%	14	3.9%	13	3.6%	1587	88.2%	13	**541.81
20	231	64.2%	88	24.4%	41	11.4%	0	0%	0	0%	1630	90.6%	6	**163.22
21	255	70.8%	59	16.4%	33	9.2%	13	3.6%	0	0%	1636	90.9%	5	**415.16
22	266	73.9%	18	5%	71	19.7%	5	1.4%	0	0%	1625	90.3%	7	**486.07
23	254	70.6%	61	16.9%	35	9.7%	10	3%	0	0%	1639	91.1%	4	**412.91

** functional at (0.01)

Table (8) illustrated participants responses (χ^2) in terms of considering legislations an indicator of values of integrity and corruption combat were all significant ($\alpha = 0.01$), the responses degrees were all very high except in items (2, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, and 17) which scored high degrees.

Items numbers, (1) "Consider all forms of corruption a crime punishable by law", (6) "There is a mechanism for systematic review for values of integrity and corruption combat measures", and (18) "Universities supervise all educational, research, administrative and financial requirements in an organized manner", scored very high agreement values, respectively (93.9, 93.6, and 92.9) as figure 1 illustrate.

Figure 1. Percent of the items that scored high values on legislations domain

While items numbers, (13) “There is a policy for media freedom and protection”, (15) “There are private independent neutral commissions responsible for hiring and promotions”, and (16) “Universities apply job rotation policy for various positions” very low responses values scoring respectively (72.8, 77.6, and 78.2) as figure 2 illustrate.

Figure 2. Percent of the items that scored low values on legislations domain

In light of table (8) results, the responses agreements values scored on the “legislations” domain range from very high - high, scoring a percent rang (72.8-93.9) which refers to a high percent. These results indicate that universities have clear legislations to combat corruption; they are issued and announced largely. This fact confirms the major role the government carries to strike the corrupt and abusers to eradicate corruption roots, dry its sources, and hold everyone involved accountable for their dirty deeds regardless of their positions, in order to move forward and benefit the country and citizens.

This result confirmed the results obtained by Mahmoud (2016), Al-Daihani (2017), Najm (2017), Makki and suriyah (2017), Boquesah and Saadi (2018) and Masghouni, et al. (2019). They all emphasized the importance of implementing the techniques of corruption combat, to activate codes of job ethics, enhance transparency and objectivity in all activities and transactions, adopt strict rules and regulations to combat corruption, all of which of the important factors to improve institutions quality and establish effective construct and productive society’s. To answer the second question of “What is the extent to which faculty teaching staff in the Universities of Saudi Arabia practice values of integrity and combating corruption?” the responses on the practices domain were collected and analyzed. Repetitions and percent of the responses are illustrated in table (9).

Table 9. Repetitions, rates, and responses (No. 360) ranks on practices

Item	Very high		High		Moderate		Weak		Very weak		Points	%	Rank	χ ²
	Chi-	%	Chi-	%	Chi-	%	Chi-	%	Chi-	%				

	square		square		square		square		square					
1	15	4.2%	93	25.8%	240	66.7%	12	3.3%	0	0%	1191	66.2%	5	380.20**
2	22	6.1%	33	9.2%	56	15.6%	237	65.8%	12	3.3%	896	49.8%	20	**487.53
3	15	4.2%	42	11.7%	50	13.9%	229	63.6%	24	6.7%	875	48.6%	21	**438.69
4	62	17.2%	238	66.1%	46	12.8%	14	3.9%	0	0%	1428	79.3%	3	**337.78
5	4	1.1%	87	24.2%	246	68.3%	19	5.3%	4	1.1%	1148	63.8%	6	**591.08
6	9	2.5%	31	8.6%	250	69.4%	49	13.6%	21	5.8%	1038	57.7%	19	**562.00
7	14	3.9%	39	10.8%	261	72.5%	30	8.3%	16	4.4%	1085	60.3%	13	**626.03
8	15	4.2%	42	11.7%	240	66.7%	44	12.2%	19	5.3%	1070	59.4%	16	**499.53
9	6	1.7%	41	11.4%	262	72.8%	28	7.8%	23	6.4%	1059	58.8%	17	**635.47
10	5	1.4%	14	3.9%	45	12.5%	238	66.1%	58	16.1%	750	41.7%	24	**504.64
11	4	1.1%	1	0.3%	45	12.5%	264	73.3%	46	12.8%	733	40.7%	25	**665.75
12	10	2.8%	43	11.9%	266	73.9%	35	9.7%	6	1.7%	1096	60.9%	11	**667.31
13	15	4.2%	40	11.1%	259	71.9%	44	12.2%	2	0.6%	1102	61.2%	10	**623.97
14	16	4.4%	43	11.9%	272	75.6%	25	6.9%	4	1.1%	1122	62.3%	9	**705.69
15	6	1.7%	32	8.9%	261	72.5%	54	15%	7	1.9%	1056	58.7%	18	**642.03
16	12	3.3%	36	10%	255	70.8%	45	12.5%	12	3.3%	1071	59.5%	15	**593.25
17	28	7.8%	263	73.1%	39	10.8%	27	7.5%	3	0.8%	1366	75.9%	4	**642.94
18	51	14.2%	261	72.5%	39	10.8%	5	1.4%	4	1.1%	1430	79.4%	2	**643.94
19	0	0%	12	3.3%	42	11.7%	271	75.3%	35	9.7%	751	41.7%	23	**490.82
20	6	1.7%	12	3.3%	41	11.4%	270	75%	31	8.6%	772	42.9%	22	**691.69
21	14	3.9%	49	13.6%	264	73.3%	33	9.2%	0	0%	1124	62.4%	8	**455.36
22	0	0%	49	13.6%	271	75.3%	28	7.8%	12	3.3%	1077	59.8%	14	**493.00
23	10	2.8%	42	11.7%	266	73.9%	34	9.4%	8	2.2%	1092	60.7%	12	**665.56
24	53	14.7%	275	76.4%	30	8.3%	2	0.6%	0	0%	1459	81.1%	1	521.53**
25	27	7.5%	46	12.8%	251	69.7%	32	8.9%	4	1.1%	1140	63.3%	7	**568.97

** functional at (0.01)

As observed in table (9), χ^2 of the participant's responses concerning the practices of the values of integrity and corruption combat are significant at (0.01), the degrees recorded for the items direction is moderate, except for items (4, 17, 18, and 24) which recorded high degrees, while items (2, 3, 10, 11, 19, and 20) degrees were weak. Items numbers (4) "Favoritism in distributing tasks, powers, and in selecting presidents, members of councils and committees", (18) "Some academic leaders exploit mandates and powers granted to them", and (24) "Withhold some information and statistics from researchers and who wish to benefit from it", recorded the highest degrees percent respectively (79.3, 79.4, and 81.1) as figure three illustrate.

Figure 3. Percent of the items that scored high values on the "practice" domain

Whereas items (11) "There are deterrent penalties for the convicted in corruption cases", (10) "There are legislations to protect whistle-blowers and counter-allegations", and (19) "The university employees performance is evaluated objectively" recorded the lowest percent is respectively (40.7, and 41.7) as figure 4 illustrate.

Figure 4. Percent of the items that scored low degrees on practices domain

To sum up in light of table (9) results, responses of the participants regarding the “practices” domain as an indicator of values of integrity and corruption combat degrees were moderate to weak; scores percent range (40.7%-81.1%). These results refer to weak practices of the indicators of values of integrity and corruption combat, the concepts are unclear and uncontrolled in individuals and institutions awareness, and do not reflect in their behavior. This may be explained by several reasons, most important of which is the weak system of values and morals, leniency in the control process, spread of a culture supportive to corruption such as flamboyant and rapid desire for richness, and spread of consumption culture while accountability and control are absence. This result is confirmed by the studies of Al-Farra (2013), Al-Kanzi (2015), Al-Shalawi (2016), and Al-Kharif (2017), all of which agreed that accountability is still weak in many institutions, this requires further justification and clarification of the decisions or practices issued. The researcher believes that even if the practices are weak to moderate, it is still far better than past times due to regulations and legislations enacted by the government and adopted by many institutions, the current study results in the domain of legislation is a good example of existence of legislations and practices.

The researcher believes that this problem is solved by strengthening religious restrains, focusing on values and morals, and spreading awareness about Islamic legislations regarding corruption issues. It is solved as well by reminding individuals of corruption consequences now and in the hereafter, identifying corruption destructive effects on comprehensive development, considering self-accountability and feelings of guilt toward irregularities of the important issues that help establish behaviours supporting integrity and honesty, and not to forget aspects of follow-up, law rule and implementing strict measures to reduce these behaviors.

To answer the third question “Is there a statistical correlation between the values of integrity and corruption combat indicators on one side and patriotism on the other from the viewpoint of the faculty teaching staff in the Universities of Saudi Arabia?” repetitions and percent of the participant’s responses are calculated as illustrated in table 10.

Table 10. Repetitions, percent, and responses (No. 360) ranks on patriotism

Item	Very high		High		Moderate		Weak		Very weak		Points	Chi-square	Rank	χ^2
	Chi-square	%	Chi-square	%	Chi-square	%	Chi-square	%	Chi-square	%				
1	262	72.8%	48	13.3%	40	11.1%	10	2.8%	0	0%	1642	91.2	5	447.20**
2	268	74.4%	49	13.6%	34	9.4%	9	2.5%	0	0%	1656	92	2	478.47**
3	13	3.6%	44	12.2%	264	73.3%	34	9.4%	5	1.4%	1106	61.4	21	653.64**
4	15	4.2%	35	9.7%	249	69.2%	47	13.1%	14	3.9%	1070	59.4	24	554.67**
5	65	18.1%	262	72.8%	21	5.8%	12	3.3%	0	0%	1460	81.1	7	456.16**
6	7	1.9%	39	10.8%	268	74.4%	37	10.3%	9	2.5%	1078	59.9	23	679.50**
7	59	16.4%	251	69.7%	35	9.7%	12	3.3%	3	0.8%	1431	79.5	11	582.50**
8	17	4.7%	48	13.3%	268	74.4%	16	4.4%	11	3.1%	1124	62.4	19	678.81**
9	80	22.2%	247	68.6%	20	5.6%	11	3.1%	2	0.6%	1472	81.8	6	583.53**
10	57	15.8%	260	72.2%	37	10.3%	6	1.7%	0	0%	1448	80.4	8	442.82**
11	45	12.5%	256	71.1%	59	16.4%	0	0%	0	0%	1426	79.2	12	232.02**
12	48	13.3%	262	72.8%	36	10%	9	2.5%	5	1.4%	1419	78.8	14	644.86**
13	18	5%	43	11.9%	272	75.6%	27	7.5%	0	0%	1132	62.9	18	494.29**
14	62	17.2%	260	72.2%	20	5.6%	18	5%	0	0%	1446	80.3	9	441.87**
15	17	4.7%	52	14.4%	269	74.7%	16	4.4%	6	1.7%	1138	63.2	17	690.64**
16	266	73.9%	52	14.4%	42	11.7%	0	0%	0	0%	1664	92.4	1	266.87**
17	14	3.9%	27	7.5%	278	77.2%	26	7.2%	15	4.2%	1079	59.9	22	777.29**

18	54	15%	266	73.9%	35	9.7%	0	0%	5	1.4%	1444	80.2	10	442.13**
19	16	4.4%	43	11.9%	268	74.4%	33	9.2%	0	0%	1122	62.3	20	473.53**
20	51	14.2%	250	69.4%	26	7.2%	17	4.7%	16	4.4%	1383	76.8	15	561.14**
21	28	7.8%	46	12.8%	265	73.6%	12	3.3%	9	2.5%	1152	64	16	658.75**
22	56	15.6%	258	71.7%	16	4.4%	30	8.3%	0	0%	1420	78.9	13	427.29**
23	267	74.2%	55	15.3%	22	6.1%	16	4.4%	0	0%	1653	91.8	4	473.93**
24	263	73.1%	51	14.2%	43	11.9%	3	0.8%	0	0%	1654	91.9	3	458.09**

** functional at (0.01)

In table (10), we observe that χ^2 of the participant’s responses about “patriotism” domain as an indicator of the values of integrity and corruption combat were significant at (0.01), the degrees direction is high, except for items (3, 4, 6, 8, 13, 15, 17, 19, and 21) which recorded moderate degrees, and items (1, 2, 16, 23, and 24) recorded very high degrees.

Items numbers (16) “I am proud of all the country landmarks and what reflects its identity and history”, (2), “I respect rules and regulations established by the work system”, and (24) “I make sure to represent my country in different occasions and events honorably” the highest percent, the scores respectively were (91.9%, 92%, and 92.4%) as figure 5 shows.

Figure 5. Percent of the items that scored high degrees in “patriotism” domain

While items (4) “I participate in solving the problems and obstacles that prevent achieving my work goals”, (6) “I am emotionally attached to the place I work in”, and (17) “I advance the public interest over my own interest” low percent, the scores respectively were (59.4, and 59.9) as figure six illustrate.

Figure 6. Percent of the items that scored low degrees on “patriotism” domain

Results in Table 10 yielded that responses on the third domain of “patriotism” were moderate to very high, percent scores were (59.4%-92.4%), and this result is an indicator of patriotism among the faculty-teaching staff in Universities of Saudi Arabia.

This result agrees with the results found by Abu El-Maati and Ahmed (2018). This result may be explained by attention volume an individual feels in his homeland, feeling safe and protected, being able to pursue ambitions and having a good quality of life. Individual feelings of patriotism increase when his political and social rights are obtained and justice and equality are felt.

The researcher believes that universities may play a prominent role in enhancing the values of national integrity through awakening potentials and competencies of academics to reformulate the concepts of integrity, accountability, and transparency and correlate these concepts with the real life. Patriot qualified academic competencies have the ability to promote institutions performance, improve levels of productivity, efficiency, discipline, laws and regulation respect and abidance by systematic standards.

Table 11. Correlation coefficients between indices of integrity values and corruption combat among the participants

Indices	Legislations	Practices	Patriotism
Legislations			
Practices	0.674**		
Patriotism	0.584**	0.649**	

As observed in table (11) there is a positive significant correlation at (0.01) between legislations and both of practices and patriotism, significant correlation is also found at (0.01) between all the domains.

To answer the fourth question "Are there significant differences between the faculty teaching staff responses in the Universities of Saudi Arabia on legislations, practices and patriotism according to academic degree obtained and affiliation?" the researcher calculated Source of Variance, Sum of Squares, Degrees of Freedom, Mean Squares, and f-value as table (11) illustrate.

Table 11. Significance of the responses differences based on their affiliation

Variables	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	f-Value	Sign.
Legislations	Between groups	353.276	4	88.319	0.773	Insignificant
	Within groups	40580.499	355	114.311		
	Overall	40933.775	359	-		
Practices	Between groups	514.463	4	128.616	1.440	Insignificant
	Within groups	31703.312	355	89.305		
	Overall	32217.775	359	-		
Patriotism	Between groups	563.394	4	140.848	1.203	Insignificant
	Within groups	41577.381	355	117.119		
	Overall	42140.775	359	-		

As observed in table (11), significant differences are not found in the participants responses on the dimensions of values of integrity and corruption combat (legislations, practices, and patriotism) attributed to the affiliation. This result is attributed to the fact that Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is an Islamic country adopting the Holy Qura'an and Prophet Mohammad peace be upon HIM Sunnah as a constitution for legislations and regulations for all institutions that consider justice and equity.

The second part of the question is answered by calculating Source of Variance, Sum of Squares, Degrees of Freedom, Mean Squares, and f-value of the participants responses on the values of integrity and corruption combat dimensions (legislations, practices, and patriotism) based on the academic degree obtained as presented in table (12).

Table 12. differences significance of participants responses based on Academic degree obtained

Variables	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	f-Value	Sign.
Legislations	Between groups	328.652	3	109.551	0.960	Insignificant
	Within groups	40605.123	356	114.059		
	Overall	40933.775	359	-		
Practices	Between groups	420.165	3	140.055	1.568	Insignificant
	Within groups	31797.610	356	89.319		
	Overall	32217.775	359	-		
Patriotism	Between groups	150.497	3	50.166	0.425	Insignificant
	Within groups	41990.278	356	117.950		
	Overall	42140.775	359	-		

It is noticed in table (12) that the differences are not significant in the participant's responses on the dimensions of values of integrity and corruption combat (legislations, practices, and patriotism) based on the academic degree obtained. This result is attributed to the fact that all the universities environments are similar, legislations are similar and they are implemented on everyone in an objective transparent manner regardless of the academic degree, this in turn reflects on the degree of practicing the behaviours of values of integrity and patriotism of the Saudi academics, which never differs by their degrees.

Results

1. The participant's responses degree in "legislations" domain was "very high" in all items. These results indicate that the Universities of Saudi Arabia have adopted regulatory legislations and clear laws to enhance the values of integrity and corruption combat.
2. The participant's responses degree in "practices" domain was "moderate" and "weak" in all items, this result refers to the weak practice of indicators of values of integrity and corruption combat.
3. The participant's responses degree in "patriotism" domain was "moderate" to "very high" in all items, this result signals strong patriotism among the faculty-teaching staff at the Universities of Saudi Arabia.
4. There is a positive significant correlation at (0.01) between "legislations" and both of "practices" and "patriotism".
5. Differences in the means of the participants responses in the dimensions of values of integrity, corruption combat (legislations, practices, and patriotism) attributed to affiliation, and academic degree obtained are not found.

Recommendations

In light of the results of the study, the researcher recommends to:

1. Increase awareness programs to enhance values of integrity and demonstrate the risks of corruption and the negative implications of its spread.
2. Focus on morals and man construction in the fight against corruption in work sectors.
3. Spread the culture of integrity and transparency because it serve the country and promote the wish to fight all corruption types that oppose patriotism.
4. Create an administration to protect integrity and correlate directly with the National Authority for Combating Corruption, and to activate its role in monitoring to ensure adherence to the values of integrity and transparency.
5. Implement job rotation for the different positions in universities and other institutions.
6. Establish private independent neutral commissions that are responsible for hiring and promotions.
7. Establish for a policy of media freedom and protection.
8. Guarantee justice and objectivity in job evaluations of the employees and faculty-teaching staff.
9. Adopt a model for administrative, academic, and financial information flow that enables managing public affairs and punish negligence to guarantee equality and rule of the law.
10. Stress the importance of establishing legislation to protect whistle-blowers and counter-allegations.
11. Emphasize the importance of setting deterrent penalties for the convicted in corruption cases.

Suggestions

- 1- Conducting a comparative study on the experiences of universities in developing and strengthening the values of integrity and combating corruption.
- 2- Conducting a study on the difficulties and obstacles facing higher education in applying corruption combating mechanisms and procedures.
- 3- Conducting a study on the impact of administrative corruption on the efforts of comprehensive development of communities.

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